

Validating Post-Quantum and Hybrid Certificate Automation Through ACME-STAR in IPsec Environments

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Abstract—The transition to post-quantum cryptography (PQC) has a direct impact on Public Key Infrastructures (PKI) and on the new type of Certificates. Modern PKIs are increasingly reliant on automated certificate management systems capable of supporting both classical and PQC algorithms. In this paper, we present an open-source implementation of the ACME-STAR protocol that enables the issuance of classical, PQC, and hybrid certificates as a transition solution. We demonstrate the functional validity of the proposed solution through its integration into IPsec environments, where it enables automated certificate delivery for mutual authentication. Our evaluation shows complete interoperability with classical peers while maintaining the PQC security properties, providing a practical path to the deployment of PQC in automated PKI systems.

Index Terms—Post-quantum cryptography, ACME-STAR, hybrid certificates, IPsec, certificate automation

I. INTRODUCTION

The deployment of post-quantum cryptography (PQC) algorithms is being driven by NIST’s standardization process, which has selected three core algorithms: ML-KEM [1], ML-DSA [2], and SLH-DSA [3], with additional candidates still under evaluation. The last two algorithms provide essential building blocks for quantum-resistant public key infrastructures (PKIs).

In parallel, standardization efforts are defining X.509 certificate formats for PQC and hybrid (classical and PQC) public keys, allowing gradual PQC migration while maintaining interoperability with existing infrastructures.

Despite this progress, automated certificate lifecycle management remains a critical gap in the PQC transition. Traditional solutions using protocols such as Certificate Management Protocol (CMP) [4] or Automated Certificate Management Environment (ACME) [5] require significant modifications to support PQC key types, Certificate Signing Requests (CSRs), and hybrid certificate formats that combine classical

and PQC algorithms. Furthermore, the use of short-lived certificates is expected to play a key role during a long transition period, providing flexibility, reduced impact of revocation, and a smoother migration from classical to PQC credentials. In this context, the ACME variants that automatically issue and renew short-lived certificates are particularly well suited.

This paper presents a functional open-source implementation that adapts the short-lived certificate variant of ACME (ACME-STAR) to support classical, PQC, and hybrid certificate delivery, as well as flexible reconfiguration of cryptographic algorithms. We validate this solution through a set of performance measurements. Additionally, we integrate the solution with IPsec, demonstrating automated certificate issuance and installation, and successful mutual authentication with classical-only, hybrid, or PQC-capable peers.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the ACME and ACME-STAR extensions for PQC and hybrid certificate support. Section III presents the developed solution including the IPsec integration architecture. Section IV details the experimental setup and evaluation, and Section V concludes the paper and outlines future work.

II. ACME PROTOCOL AND PQ/T CERTIFICATES

A. ACME Protocol Overview

ACME enables automated certificate issuance through a client-server model. Its core workflow includes account registration, authorization challenges, CSR submission, and certificate issuance. To ensure the integrity and authenticity of the transactions, all content exchanged between the client and the Certificate Authority (CA) is protected using JSON Web Signatures (JWS). ACME-STAR [6] extends this framework to support short-term automatic renewal, which is critical for maintaining security in crypto-agile credential environments.

B. Profile for Delegated Certificates

ACME-STAR also allows generate delegated certificates [7]. This profile addresses the security risks associated with sharing private keys in distributed environments, such as a Content Delivery Network (CDN) terminating TLS sessions for a Content Owner (e.g., Netflix). In this architecture, the Identity Owner (IdO) assumes a dual role: it acts as a specialized ACME-STAR server for the delegate (i.e., the CDN node), while simultaneously operating as an ACME-STAR client with respect to the upstream CA.

Fig. 1: ACME-STAR (left) and Delegation (right) workflow for certificate issuance.

Fig. 1 show a comparison between the ACME-STAR (non-delegated) and the delegated ACME-STAR workflow for certificate issuance.

In the first case, the ACME client directly interacts with the ACME server to create a STAR order, complete the required authorization challenges and submit a CSR. Upon successful validation, the ACME server provides a certificate URL from which the client periodically retrieves renewed short-term certificates. Certificate renewal is handled automatically by the ACME server throughout the validity period.

In the delegated ACME-STAR, the workflow is initiated by the Name Delegation Consumer (NDC), which uses its account on the IdO ACME-STAR server to create an order and submit the CSR. In this profile, no authorization challenges are performed between the NDC and the IdO.

Once the request is verified, the IdO acts as an ACME Client towards the CA. The IdO is responsible for completing all required authorization challenges with the CA and subsequently finalizing the order using the CSR originally provided by the NDC. As in the non-delegated case, the CA issues a STAR certificate accessible via a certificate URL, from which the NDC periodically retrieves renewed certificates without further authentication.

A critical security property of the delegated ACME-STAR is that the IdO never has access to the private key associated with the issued certificate, thereby maintaining the delegate’s operational security. However, as the owner of the ACME account and the private keys used to authenticate with the CA, the IdO retains full control over the certificate’s lifecycle. Consequently, the IdO can terminate or suspend the automatic STAR renewal process at any time, ensuring that the delegation remains under the strict governance of the IdO.

C. PQC and Hybrid Certificate Extensions

To support the transition from traditional to post-quantum cryptography, several certificate types can be used. The IETF [8] has made a taxonomy on the alternatives. A **traditional certificate** contains a single classical public key (e.g. ECDSA), while a **post-quantum certificate** carries a single PQC public key such as ML-DSA. To mitigate the risk of deploying unproven PQC algorithms, **PQ/T(PostQuantum/Traditional) hybrid certificates** embed public keys for both algorithm families within a single certificate structure, with component keys either combined into a composite public key or carried individually via certificate extensions.

III. TECHNICAL SOLUTION AND TEST SETUP

A. PQC and Hybrid Certificates with ACME

Building upon previous taxonomy, the architecture implemented in this work provides crypto-agility by supporting five distinct certificate models that collectively cover the full migration spectrum, from full backward compatibility to pure post-quantum security:

- **Classic:** Standard ECC or RSA models used to maintain full compatibility with classic systems and traditional network infrastructures.
- **PQC:** A pure post-quantum model based on ML-DSA signatures, designed for environments where classical algorithms are no longer considered secure [9].
- **Composite:** A hybrid approach that introduces a new public key structure based on the concatenation of classical and PQC material. This enforces a *strong* transition, as both endpoints must recognize the combined key format to establish a connection [10].
- **Chameleon:** A migration model based on the concept of delta certificates, which are reconstructed based on the differences relative to the base certificate. This model is based on the non-critical *deltaCertificateDescriptor* extension to store the necessary data for the derivation of the post-quantum identity [11].

- **Chimera:** A hybrid model that utilizes three distinct X.509 extensions (*altSubjectPublicKeyInfo*, *altSignatureAlgorithm*, and *altSignatureValue*) to represent an alternative post-quantum signature alongside the classical one. This enables a *smooth* transition where traditional systems ignore the extensions while modern ones validate the alternative signature [12].

TABLE I: Implemented Certificate Models and Migration Strategies

Model	Migration Path	Technical Approach
Classic	Traditional support	Standard RSA/ECDSA
PQC	Pure quantum-safe	ML-DSA (Dilithium)
Composite	Strong transition	Combined Public Key Structure
Chameleon	Smooth transition	Non-critical X.509 Extension
Chimera	Medium transition	Critical/Non-critical X.509 Extension

The implementation extends a Java-based open-source acmeserver project [13] with ACME-STAR support (including delegate profiles), leveraging BouncyCastle 1.79+ with native PQC algorithm support. To manage this diversity without modifying the ACME-STAR protocol, a backend routing module was implemented. This module intercepts the CSR sent by the client, identifies the requested key type or extension, and dynamically routes the request to one of five independent Root CAs. Each Root CA is dedicated to a specific certificate type and maintains its own independent intermediate chain with unique keys, thereby ensuring the integrity and isolation of the validation process while remaining fully compliant with standard ACME-STAR workflows.

Furthermore, to guarantee application-level PQC protection within the control plane, ML-DSA signatures were implemented into the JWS layer. This implementation follows the specifications of the ML-DSA for JOSE and COSE draft [14], which defines a new key type structure for quantum-resistant signatures. By integrating these post-quantum signatures into the JWS-authenticated exchanges, the architecture ensures that the entire certificate management lifecycle, and not just the issued credentials, remains resilient against quantum-capable adversaries.

B. IPsec Authentication Architecture

IKEv2 in IPsec relies on X.509 certificates for peer authentication [15]. Whereas traditional deployments depend on static RSA/ECDSA credentials and manual certificate management, the proposed approach automates the certificate lifecycle through the integration of ACME-STAR-issued PQC and hybrid certificates.

To validate the proposed architecture, a testing environment based on IPsec tunnels was deployed. StrongSwan [16] was selected as the reference platform due to its modularity and its established support for post-quantum key exchanges (ML-KEM) and signatures (ML-DSA). Although the Chimera model has already been standardized by the ITU-T X.509, other hybrid approaches, such as Composite and Chameleon, are still undergoing standardization. Despite the official status

of the Chimera model, native support for these structures is currently absent from the project’s core. Consequently, the source code was extended to add support for the Chimera model, taking advantage of its status as an established international standard.

To this end, a dedicated plugin for the strongSwan v5.9.14 framework, named *chimera*, was developed. This plugin extends the IKE_AUTH phase, enabling the cryptographic engine to recognize and validate dual-signature structures. The implementation focuses on the extraction and verification of four critical components within the certificate:

- **altSubjectPublicKeyInfo:** A critical or non-critical extension containing the alternative public key associated with the certificate subject. The raw key material is encoded following the standard *SubjectPublicKeyInfo* structure.
- **altSignatureAlgorithm:** An extension containing the Object Identifier (OID) that specifies the alternative signature scheme employed (e.g., ML-DSA).
- **altSignatureValue:** An extension containing the digital signature generated by the alternative algorithm, which is essential for the hybrid validation process.
- **Signature Validation:** The process used to verify the alternative signature. For this purpose, an alternative To-Be-Signed (TBS) certificate structure is reconstructed, following the original format but omitting the primary signature algorithm and the *altSignatureValue* extension to ensure a valid input for the post-quantum verification engine.

Finally, re-authentication is enforced during each CHILD_SA renegotiation. This mechanism ensures that any rotation of short-lived PQC credentials, facilitated by the ACME-STAR automation, is immediately effective across the network infrastructure.

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

A. Test Methodology

The proposed architecture is evaluated through four test scenarios covering both computational efficiency and the operational impact of the PQC transition. ACME-STAR without delegation was selected, as the core certificate request/issuance process remains equivalent across both modes, focusing the analysis of PQC overhead in STAR certificate lifecycle operations.

First, the *Certificate Creation Time* test measures the CA’s processing capacity by timing the complete ACME-STAR flow, from account registration to certificate issuance.

Second, the *Migration Time* test measures the time required to replace a classical certificate with one of the four new models (PQC, Composite, Chimera, or Chameleon). Together, these two experiments identify computational bottlenecks, especially in signature generation.

Third, the *Network Impact* test compares the traffic generated by classical and PQC-based certificates on the CA’s network interface. Finally, the *IPsec Functional Validation* test

evaluates whether the modified strongSwan engine can handle IKEv2 fragmentation and dual authentication in realistic tunnel scenarios. As shown in Table II, the larger size of PQC and hybrid certificates motivates the network-related tests.

TABLE II: Storage Size of the Different Certificate Types

Certificate Type	Size (Bytes)
Classic (ECDSA P-384)	717
PQC (ML-DSA-44)	4,108
Composite	4,446
Chimera	4,525
Chameleon	4,608

B. Analysis of Results and Key Findings

The experimental results for certificate processing are summarized in Table III. The data reveals a surprising consistency across all models; the CA’s processing time for post-quantum and hybrid signatures does not show a significant increase compared to classical algorithms. In fact, the average creation time for a Composite certificate is slightly lower than the Classic model, suggesting that the total latency is dominated by the ACME-STAR protocol overhead and network handshakes rather than the cryptographic computation itself. Migration times follow a similar pattern, with all transitions completing in under 100 ms, proving the system’s agility for rapid credential rotation.

TABLE III: Mean and Median Processing Times (ms)

Model	Creation Time		Migration Time	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median
Classic	85.40	81.00	—	—
PQC	78.11	73.50	82.60	80.00
Composite	78.08	72.00	74.80	68.00
Chimera	82.40	76.00	82.60	76.00
Chameleon	90.50	86.50	90.00	87.50

The comparative analysis of creation and migration latencies is further illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Mean and Median Processing times.

The bar chart confirms that all certificate models operate within a narrow performance window, consistently ranging between 70 and 90 ms. Notably, the Chameleon model exhibits the highest average latency, approaching the 90 ms threshold, whereas the Composite and PQC models demonstrate performance levels that are highly competitive with the Classic standard. Furthermore, the fact that median values remain consistently lower than the mean across all categories indicates a stable processing environment with minimal influence from extreme outliers, reinforcing the feasibility of these post-quantum and hybrid models for high-frequency automated issuance.

The primary bottleneck identified across all models is network throughput. To provide a consolidated comparison, Figs. 3 and 4 present the input and output throughput, respectively, for all certificate types under identical workload conditions.

Throughput measurements were obtained using the `ifstat` tool over a fixed observation window of 15 seconds, while a stress test was simultaneously triggered from the Identity Owner web interface. This setup generates a continuous stream of certificate issuance requests from the ACME-STAR client to the server, allowing the evaluation of sustained network behaviour under load.

It is important to note that the number of certificates issued within this time window is not fixed, as it depends on both the certificate type and current network conditions. In particular, larger certificate structures (e.g., PQC or hybrid models) inherently reduce the number of requests that can be processed within the same time interval. Achieving a fixed number of issued certificates across all models would require adjusting the measurement window individually for each certificate type, which would not allow direct comparability of throughput results.

Fig. 3: Network throughput during certificate creation (input traffic).

From the input throughput perspective (Fig. 3), the classic

model maintains a highly stable and predictable traffic pattern. Other models also exhibit relatively stable behaviour, with values typically ranging between 500 and 750 kB/s. This indicates that inbound traffic, primarily associated with request handling and protocol signalling, is not significantly affected by the certificate structure or size.

Fig. 4: Network throughput during certificate creation (output traffic).

In contrast, the output throughput (Fig. 4) reveals substantial differences across models, highlighting the impact of certificate size and structural complexity.

The Classic model maintains the lowest and most stable output traffic, consistently remaining below 500 kB/s, reflecting the compact nature of traditional ECDSA-based certificates.

Hybrid and post-quantum approaches introduce a notable increase in network demand. The Composite and Chameleon models exhibit intermediate behaviour, with output peaks frequently reaching between 1500 and 1700 kB/s, driven by the additional data required to carry multiple cryptographic components or extensions. In particular, in the Chameleon model, the use of the *deltaCertificateDescriptor* extension contributes directly to this overhead by embedding additional certificate data within the transmission. This represents almost a four-fold increase in data volume compared to the classic standard, confirming that while computational cost of PQC remains low, the network infrastructure must be adequately provisioned to handle the increased size of post-quantum credentials.

The Chimera model further amplifies this trend, with output peaks exceeding 2000 kB/s. This behaviour is attributed to its more complex certificate structure, which incorporates three distinct X.509 extensions to represent the alternative signatures, increasing the transmitted data volume. This result confirms that the structural complexity of Chimera certificates, while beneficial for standards compliance, directly contributes to a substantial increase in the bandwidth required for the `IKE_AUTH` exchange.

Finally, the PQC model demonstrates the highest throughput requirements among all evaluated approaches. Output traffic frequently reaches peak near and above 2000 kB/s, confirming that the transmission overhead is dominated by the significantly larger size of pure post-quantum certificates (e.g., ML-DSA-44). Despite this, input throughput remains comparable to other models, reinforcing that the network load is primarily driven by certificate delivery rather than request processing.

As shown in Table IV, the input throughput (requests from the client) remains uniform across all models, as the size of the CSR varies only slightly. However, the output throughput scales dramatically with PQC integration. The PQC and Chimera models represent the highest load, requiring up to four times the bandwidth of classic systems. These findings confirm that while PQC signature processing is optimized for production, the infrastructure must be provisioned to handle increased data volumes during certificate delivery.

TABLE IV: Average Network Throughput per Certificate Type (kB/s)

Model	Input (kB/s)	Output (kB/s)
Classic	223.30	410.50
PQC	647.00	1596.60
Composite	581.00	1382.30
Chimera	635.20	1470.60
Chameleon	606.70	1307.10

The increase in certificate size and network throughput previously analyzed has a direct impact on protocol behavior, as evidenced during the IPsec functional validation. Summarized in Table V, the Classic model exchange remains within standard limits requiring only one packet. On the other hand, the PQC and Chimera models force the `IKE_AUTH` response to be divided into 5 and 6 fragments. This correlation confirms that the network overhead is the primary operational challenge for implementing quantum-safe industrial tunnels, requiring robust fragmentation handling in the underlying IPsec engine.

TABLE V: IPsec `IKE_AUTH` Fragmentation Results

Model	<code>IKE_AUTH</code> Packets	Fragmentation Status
Classic	1	None
PQC	5	Fragmented
Chimera	6	Fragmented

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A functional open-source architecture for automated post-quantum and hybrid certificate management has been presented and validated through IPsec IKEv2 integration. The implementation of the ACME-STAR protocol, combined with a specialized delegation profile, enables a high degree of crypto-agility, allowing Identity Owners to maintain strict governance over the certificate lifecycle without compromising the private key sovereignty of distributed delegates.

The development and validation of this architecture opens several paths for future research, which include:

- Integration with TLS 1.3 to achieve broader protocol coverage and ensure quantum-safe handshakes across web services.
- Continuous alignment with emerging IETF PQC certificate standards to maintain interoperability as hybrid models evolve.
- Extension of the framework to support the Certificate Management Protocol (CMP) and other industry-standard certificate lifecycle management systems.
- Implementation and evaluation of hybrid signature schemes for both transport-layer (TLS) and application-layer (JWS) protocols to ensure end-to-end crypto-agility.

Experimental results demonstrate that the computational overhead introduced by PQC and hybrid signature processing is negligible, with issuance and migration times consistently remaining under 100 ms, as detailed in Table III. However, the transition poses significant challenges for network infrastructure. The nearly four-fold increase in output throughput and the requirement for IKEv2 fragmentation, reaching up to six fragments for the Chimera model, identify bandwidth capacity and robust protocol handling as the primary operational requirements for quantum-safe communication tunnels. Overall, the system provides a practical and interoperable pathway for the deployment of automated, quantum-resistant PKI in industrial environments.

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